

TEACHERS' SELF-CONFIDENCE, SOCIAL SKILLS, AND STRESS MANAGEMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: Biology is an important subject in senior secondary school and prerequisite subject for many fields of learning which involves medicine and surgery, anatomy, nursing and basic medical sciences, forestry and agriculture, bio-technology and so on. Despite the importance of biology, there are several difficulties associated with the learning of biology in senior secondary schools as identified by WASSCE chief examiners reports. These identified weaknesses and recommended solutions by the WAEC chief examiner diminish the work done in the classroom and cast doubt on the credibility and quality of biology teachers' job performance. This study is essential to provide information on how the combination of teachers' stress management, social ability and self-concept determine biology teachers' job performance, especially among teachers in Lagos state.

This study adopted a correlation survey research design. The study population comprised 800 Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State of Nigeria. Using Krejcie and

Morgan (1970) sample size determination, 350 Biology teachers were selected. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted as the sampling technique procedure. The research instruments for the study are Teachers Job Performance Scale ($r = 0.632$), Teachers' Social Ability Scale ($r = 0.625$), Stress Management Questionnaire ($r = 0.786$) and Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale ($r = 0.606$). Data was collected and analysed using person product moment correlation and multiple regression analysis.

Results showed that 1) there is a significant relationship between teachers' stress management and job performance; 2) there is a significant relationship between teachers' social ability and job performance; 3) there is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and job performance; 4) teachers' stress management, social ability and self-efficacy are not significant determinants of Job Performance.

The study concluded that although psychosocial variables such as stress management, social ability, and self-efficacy contribute to teachers' professional functioning, they play only a limited role in determining teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Lagos State. These teachers' variables are not significant or major factors of planning for improved teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Lagos state.

Keywords: *Job Performance, Biology, Self-confidence, Social Skills, & Stress Management*

INTRODUCTION

Biology is a subject in senior secondary school education which involves the study of living things and the understanding of the living organisms around the world. It is a natural science taught in Nigerian senior secondary schools to equip the learners with skills of understanding and managing nature and providing good health facilities, understanding the anatomy and physiology of plant and animal. Furthermore, it is important for learning science-related occupations such as medicine, nursing, pharmacy etc. (John, et. al., 2019; Reiser, 2024; Olalekan, et. al., 2025). Biology is a prerequisite subject for many fields of learning which involves medicine and surgery, anatomy, nursing and basic medical sciences, forestry and agriculture, bio-technology and so on (Ellah & Nwankwo, 2023). Despite the importance of biology,

there are several difficulties associated with the learning of biology in senior secondary schools in Nigeria as identified by WASSCE chief examiners reports (WAEC, 2023). These identified weaknesses and recommended solutions by the chief examiner diminish the work done in the classroom and cast doubt on the credibility and quality of biology teachers' job performance.

Job performance has been severally defined by researchers and authors in nearly all fields of endeavour. Koopmans et al., (2021) describe job performance as the complete anticipated worth or value to a company of the discrete social episodes that a person does over a standard timeframe. Put differently, job performance is expected quality and quantity of output arising from an individual effort on a particular job (Campbell & Wiernik, 2019). Other definitions include those of Demerouti and Bakker (2022) who defined job performance as how well individuals perform their jobs in relation to standards. Several studies have been carried out to ascertain the influence of certain variables on job performance and these factors include Job stress (Harms, et. al., 2019; Collie, 2021); social skills (Tapia-Gutierrez, & Cubo-Delgado, 2015; Ukala, 2019; Guerra-Bustamante et. al., 2019) among others.

One of the identified variable capable of affecting teachers' job performance is stress management. Stress is regarded as physiological and psychological responses that occur when people perceived the imbalance between demands placed in them and their ability to cope (Collie, 2021). These demands could either stimulate or threatens the individuals. Similarly, stress is regarded as the reaction of individuals to external and internal demands imposed upon them within the environment (American psychological association, 2023). Teaching could also be associated with high levels of stress (Schwarzer & Hallum, 2008; OECD, 2020; Collie, 2021) and teachers' work stress is an indication of unpleasant emotions because of teaching work (Harmsen, et. al., 2018). Within the teaching profession, stress is particularly prevalent due to the complex and demanding nature of the job. Teaching involves continuous interaction with students, colleagues, administrators, and parents, often under conditions of limited resources and high expectations. As a result, teaching is widely regarded as a high-stress profession (Collie, 2021; Herman et al., 2020). Sources of teacher stress are multifaceted and include workload, time pressure, student misbehaviour, lack of

administrative support, role conflict, and insufficient recognition (Herman et al., 2020; OECD, 2020). Empirical studies indicate that a significant proportion of teachers experience moderate to high levels of stress, which can adversely affect their professional effectiveness and personal well-being (Collie, 2021). The consequences of teacher stress are far-reaching. High levels of stress have been associated with burnout, reduced job satisfaction, lower teaching efficacy, and weakened teacher–student relationships (Aloe et al., 2019). Additionally, prolonged stress can negatively impact teachers’ physical and mental health, leading to absenteeism, attrition, and reduced productivity (McEwen, 2019). These outcomes highlight the importance of addressing stress within the teaching profession.

Social ability or, social skills is another variable considered in this study and have been severally defined by different researchers. Coronado (2009) expressed that they are a collection of capacities to produce good ways of behaving in relational circumstances with the target of getting satisfying reactions from others. Denham (2018) characterizes social skills as the capacity to communicate with others in a given social setting, in a characterized way and that is acknowledged or esteemed socially, being likewise helpful to other people. An important scholar defines social skills as the set of ways of behaving that express the feelings, mentalities, wants, rights, or privileges of a person in a relational setting yet regarding the ways of behaving of others tackling current issues and decreasing future troubles (Caballo, 2017). As seen, a single meaning of the social skills concept is not in existence; however, they share the reality of referring to capacities and people’s ways of behaving, and not a personality trait. These skills have been organised to form a more comprehensive model for understanding and assessing social skills among teachers. According to Manrique (2016), the indicators of social skills in teachers could include: Assertive Communication, Leadership, Conflict Resolution, and Planning. Social skills are very important for the teaching profession and they have been reported to have an impact on learning, interpersonal relations, coexistence, mental health and the collaboration of students and teachers as well as in teacher's effectiveness (Tapia-Gutierrez & Cubo-Delgado, 2015; Aldrup, et. al., 2020; OECD, 2020). Social skills are also commonly found to have significant relationship between conscientiousness and work performance, and social skill also found to

moderate the association among mental health, job performance and pay (Ferris, et al 2001; Miao, et. al., 2020; Denham, et. al., 2020). Therefore, attempt to improve teachers job performance, with the aim of improving students' learning outcomes should likely not only focus on the academic competencies of a teacher, but also take into consideration, the social abilities of the teacher.

Another important variable affecting job performance of teachers is their self-concept or self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is a feeling of satisfaction that one has in himself or herself, or confidence (the second concept) and satisfaction in oneself, and self-respect (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). Self-esteem, another concept, has been conceived as the individual's evaluation of discrepancy between self-image and ideal self. These three concepts have been used by different commentators sometimes to mean the same things and by others differently. Self-efficacy is the belief one has in being able to execute a specific task successfully (e.g., solving a math problem) in order to obtain a certain outcome (e.g., self-satisfaction or teacher recognition) and, thus, can be considered as situational specific self-confidence (Orth & Robins, 2022). Self-confidence is one of the most influential regulators of behaviour in people's everyday lives. In educational settings, Teachers with high self-confidence tend to create supportive classroom environments, demonstrate effective instructional strategies, and enhance student achievement (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001; OECD, 2019). Furthermore, teacher self-confidence is associated with important psychological outcomes because higher teacher self-efficacy predicts lower burnout, improved well-being, and greater job satisfaction (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017; Zee & Koomen, 2016). Although the studies on self-confidence (self-efficacy) have been focused on the learners; few studies have focused on teachers' self-confidence, and how it is associated with job satisfaction and performance (Bandura, 1977, Bandura, 1986; Zee, & Koomen, 2016; Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020; Collie, 2021).

From the aforementioned, this study is essential to provide information on how the combination of teachers' stress management, social ability and self-concept determine biology teachers' job performance, especially among teachers in Lagos state due to the existing knowledge and population gap in studies reviewed and

dearth of literature reflecting the combined prediction of biology teachers' job performance using their stress management, social ability and self-concept

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study investigated how teachers' self-confidence, social skills, and stress management could determine teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Lagos state, Nigeria. Specifically, it seeks to

- a. Ascertain the extent of relationship between teachers' stress management and their job performance
- b. Ascertain the extent of relationship between teachers' social ability and their job performance
- c. Ascertain the extent of relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and their job performance
- d. Examine how teachers' stress management, social ability and self-efficacy will significantly determine job performance

STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' stress management and their job performance
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' social ability and their job performance
3. There is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and their job performance
4. Teachers' stress management, social ability and self-efficacy will not significantly determine job performance

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlation survey research design. Correlation design ascertains the degree of association between two or more variables. Also, it helps to ascertain how a variable can be predicted by one or more variables.

The targeted population for the study comprised eight hundred (800) Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State of Nigeria. Using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination, three hundred and fifty (350) Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State were selected. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted as the sampling technique procedure for the study.

The research instruments for the study are Teachers Job Performance Scale (TJPS), Teachers' Social Ability Scale (TSAS), Stress Management Questionnaire (SMQ) and Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale (TSES). Teachers Job Performance Scale (TJPS) is a 25-item questionnaire with four response options. It was adapted from the TJPS developed by Hanif and Pervez (2004) and designed to measure teachers' job performance. Also, Teachers' Social Ability Scale (TSAS) is a four-point likert scale questionnaire and it contains 35 items eliciting information on teachers' social ability. Stress Management Questionnaire (SMQ) is a self-report instrument adapted from Cartwright & Cooper (1997). SMQ contains 25 items designed to measure coping strategies on a 4-point scale. Finally, Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale (TSES) is a self-report instrument, which was adopted from Bandura self-efficacy instrument by Bandura, (1997). The reliability of TJPS, TSAS, SMQ and TSES was determined by administering them on 40 Biology teachers outside the sample group. Cronbach's alpha statistics was computed and the reliability coefficients are 0.632, 0.625, 0.786 and 0.606 respectively.

The data collected was analysed using person product moment correlation and multiple Regression Analysis.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between stress management and job performance

Table 1: Correlation between teachers' stress management and Job Performance

Variables	n	R	P
Self-motivation * Job Performance	350	-0.095	0.038

Table 1 presents the relationship between teachers' stress management and job performance. From the table, there is a significant relationship between teachers' stress management and job performance ($n = 350$, $r = -0.095$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Also, there is a low and inverse relationship between teachers' stress management and job performance ($r = -0.095$).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between social ability and job performance

Table 2: Correlation analysis between teachers' social ability and Job Performance

Variables	n	R	P
Social ability * Job Performance	350	-0.117	0.014

Table 2 presents the relationship between teachers' social ability and job performance. From the table, there is a significant relationship between teachers' social ability and job performance ($n = 350$, $r = -0.117$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Also, there is a low and inverse relationship between teachers' social ability and job performance ($r = -0.117$).

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and job performance

Table 3: Correlation analysis between teachers' self-efficacy and Job Performance

Variables	n	R	P
Self-efficacy * Job Performance	350	-0.061	0.129

Table 3 presents the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and job performance. From the table, there is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and job performance ($n = 350$, $r = -0.061$, $p > 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is retained. Also, there is a low and inverse relationship between teachers' social ability and job performance ($r = -0.061$).

Hypothesis 4: Teachers' stress management, social ability and self-efficacy will not significantly determine job performance

Table 4: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	1542.775	3	514.258	2.031	.109 ^b
	Residual	87627.614	346	253.259		
	Total	89170.389	349			

$$R = 0.132; R^2 = 0.017$$

Table 4 presents the combined prediction of teachers' Job Performance using their stress management, social ability and self-efficacy. From the table, the result showed no significant outcome ($R = 0.132$, $F_{(3, 346)} = 2.031$, $P > 0.05$). It means teachers' Stress management, social ability and self-efficacy are not significant determinants of Job Performance. Hence, the null hypothesis is retained. Also, at $R^2 = 0.017$, teachers' Stress management, social ability and self-efficacy accounted for 1.7% of variance in job performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

1. Relationship between Teachers' Stress Management and Job Performance

The finding of this study revealed that there is a significant relationship between teachers' stress management and job performance. However, the relationship was low and inverse. The inverse relationship suggests that poor stress management among teachers may contribute to lower job performance in secondary schools. The finding may be attributed to the demanding nature of the teaching profession, which exposes teachers to excessive workload, classroom management difficulties, administrative pressures, and emotional exhaustion. Teachers who are unable to cope effectively with occupational stress may experience burnout, reduced concentration, low commitment to duties, and poor instructional effectiveness, thereby affecting their overall job performance. Although the relationship was weak, the significance indicates that stress management remains an important factor in determining teachers' effectiveness. The finding is consistent with the study of Xu and Jia (2022), who found that teachers' stress negatively influenced engagement and contributed to

emotional exhaustion, which in turn affected job effectiveness. Similarly, Duan, Bissaker, and Xu (2024) reported that teachers who experienced high stress levels demonstrated lower classroom effectiveness and reduced professional performance. The finding also agrees with Oclarit, and Agoylo (2024), who emphasized that effective stress management strategies improve teachers' emotional stability and work productivity.

2. Relationship between Teachers' Social Ability and Job Performance

The study also found that there is a significant relationship between teachers' social ability and job performance. The result further revealed a low and inverse relationship between teachers' social ability and job performance. This means that although teachers' social ability significantly relates to their job performance, the relationship is weak and negative. Social ability is important in the teaching profession because teachers interact continuously with students, colleagues, parents, and school administrators. Effective social interaction enhances communication, collaboration, classroom management, and teacher–student relationships. The inverse relationship obtained in this study may suggest that teachers with inadequate social skills may encounter interpersonal conflicts, poor communication, and reduced collaboration, which may negatively affect their professional performance. The finding supports the work of Zeljka, Sliskovic, and Buric (2025), who found that teachers' social and emotional competencies significantly influenced their effectiveness and reduced burnout. The finding is also in agreement with Oclarit, and Agoylo (2024), who reported that teachers with stronger social and emotional competencies demonstrated better professional adjustment and workplace effectiveness.

3. Relationship between Teachers' Self-Efficacy and Job Performance

The finding revealed that there is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and job performance. The result further showed a low and inverse relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and job performance. This finding may be due to the influence of external factors within the school system that limit the extent to which self-efficacy translates into actual performance. Consequently, even

teachers with high self-efficacy may still experience poor job performance due to unfavourable work conditions. Nevertheless, the finding may suggest that self-efficacy alone is insufficient to determine teachers' job performance in Lagos State secondary schools. It is possible that institutional and environmental conditions play more dominant roles in shaping teachers' effectiveness than personal confidence alone. The finding contradicts the study of Zakariya and Adegoke (2024), who found that teachers' self-efficacy positively influenced instructional practices and job satisfaction. The finding also disagrees with Duan, et al. (2024), who reported that self-efficacy contributes significantly to classroom management effectiveness and teaching performance.

4. Joint Contribution of Stress Management, Social Ability, and Self-Efficacy to Job Performance

The finding showed that teachers' stress management, social ability, and self-efficacy were not significant determinants of teachers' job performance. The study further revealed that the three variables jointly accounted for only 1.7% of the variance in teachers' job performance. This implies that the combined influence of stress management, social ability, and self-efficacy on teachers' job performance was very minimal. The low percentage of variance explained indicates that a larger proportion of teachers' job performance may be influenced by other factors not included in this study. Therefore, the finding implies that improving teachers' job performance in secondary schools requires a broader approach that combines psychological support with improved working conditions, adequate motivation, administrative support, and favourable educational policies. This finding suggests that teachers' job performance is multidimensional and cannot be adequately explained by psychosocial variables alone. The finding corroborates with Dang, Nguyen, and Pham (2024) who observed that school climate and organizational conditions strongly influence teachers' job satisfaction and effectiveness beyond personal psychological factors.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated how teachers' self-confidence, social skills, and stress management could serve as determinants of teachers' job performance in secondary

schools of Lagos state, Nigeria. Teachers' self-confidence had a non-significant, low, and inverse relationship with job performance; while social skills, and stress management had a significant, low, and inverse relationship with job performance. However, these teachers' variables (self-confidence, social skills, & stress management) are not significant or major factors of planning for improved teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Lagos state, Nigeria. Overall, the study concluded that although psychosocial variables such as stress management, social ability, and self-efficacy contribute to teachers' professional functioning, they play only a limited role in determining teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Lagos State. Therefore, improving teachers' job performance requires a more comprehensive approach that addresses both personal and institutional factors affecting teachers in the educational system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School administrators should organize regular stress management programmes, seminars, and counselling services for teachers to help them cope with stress related activities on the job and improve emotional well-being.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to develop positive coping strategies such as time management, teamwork, relaxation techniques, and professional support systems to reduce work-related stress and enhance job effectiveness.
3. The government and school authorities should create opportunities for teachers to improve their social and interpersonal skills through workshops, group activities, communication training, and collaborative professional programmes.
4. School principals should promote healthy interpersonal relationships and teamwork among teachers to encourage effective communication and cooperation.
5. Counsellors and educational psychologists should be employed in schools to provide psychological support services that will assist teachers in handling stress, emotional challenges, and workplace pressures.

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